

Agroforestry in Belgium

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Agroforestry as answer to requirements of policy within the EU
- Public policies without adequate strategy
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation non adapted to new productive and processing models.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Belgium		Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,10%
Nut level:	1		Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Eurostat code:	BE2		Kitchen gardens	0,85%	0,35%
Area (km ²):	13.429		Holding type	2016	2023
Population	2018	2022	Natural person (ha)	492.430	462.140
Population	6.559.294	6.709.787	Legal person (ha)	128.110	154.450
Density (p km ⁻²)	488	500	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	-
Cover data	2018	2022	Natural person (holder)	19.720	17.000
Forest	19,14%	15,95%	Legal person (holder)	4.260	4.760
Arable land	30,01%	28,44%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	-
Permanent crops	0,24%	0,13%	Regional Used Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Agroforestry	4,80%	5,50%	Farm number	23.980	21.760
Shrubland	0,97%	0,86%	Farm ha (UAA)	620.530	616.600
Grassland	24,91%	27,33%	Animal populations (Thousand head)	2018	2023
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			
Silvopasture	3,95%	5,05%			

Live bovine animals	1.283	1.234
Dairy cows	331	347
Non dairy cows	165	137
Live swine, domestic species	5.832	5.037
Live sheep	-	-
Live goats	-	-

CROPS (Hectares)	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	620.530	616.600
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	139.150	137.760
Common wheat and spelt	70.690	71.210
Durum wheat	-	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	220	540
Barley	17.760	18.180
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	550	260
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	47.360	45.670
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	500	1.910
Industrial crops	6.640	5.770
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	30	40
Fibre crops	-	4.120
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	-	380
Plants harvested green from arable land	173.100	168.750

Green maize	117.480	116.080
Kitchen gardens	-	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	2
Forestry	0
Crop diversification including woody perennials	2
Crop rotation including woody perennials	0
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	0
Interventions	2

María Rosa Mosquera Losada, Ana Couso Viana, Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro, Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez & José Javier Santiago Freijanes (2025) Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

References

- Coverland data and Agroforestry practice cover: EUROSTAT LAND COVER/USE STATISTICS (LUCAS). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas/database/primary-data>
- Demographics and Farmland data: Eurostat, <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>
- Area by NUTS 3 region (demo_r_d3area) https://doi.org/10.2908/REG_ARFA3
- Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region (demo_r_d2jan) https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_R_D2JAN
- Key farm variables area livestock (LSU) labour force and standard output (SO) by agricultural size of farm (UAA) legal status of holding and NUTS 2 regions (ef_kvaareg) https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_KVAAREG
- Farms and hectares by crops, utilised agricultural area, economic size of the farm and NUTS 2 region [ef_lus_allcrops_custom_21007488] https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_LUS_ALLCROPS
- Animal populations (December) by NUTS 2 regions [agr_r_animal] https://doi.org/10.2908/AGR_R_ANIMAL
- CAP Strategic Plans by country https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans_en#cap-strategic-plans-by-country